

Conference Abstract

Combining stable isotopes in tree rings and ecosystem fluxes to assess the effects of nitrogen deposition and climate extremes on European forests

Rossella Guerrieri[‡], Marco Montedoro[‡], Matteo Rossi[§], Francesco Mazzenga[§], Mika Aurela[‡], Daniel Berveille[¶], Nina Buchmann[#], Matthias Cuntz[¶], Nicolas Delpierre[¶], Iris Feigenwinter[«], Giacomo Gerosa[»], Andreas Ibrom[^], Fran Lauriks[˘], Milja Männikkö[‡], Riccardo Marzuoli[‡], Michiel van der Molen[‡], Leonardo Montagnani[?], Johan Neiryck[‡], Elena Vanguelova[‡], Arne Verstraeten[‡], Peter Waldner[‡], Giorgio Matteucci[§]

[‡] University of Bologna, Bologna, Italy

[§] Institute of BioEconomy, National Research Council of Italy, Rome, Italy

[‡] Finnish Meteorological Institute, Helsinki, Finland

[¶] University of Paris-Saclay, Gif-sur-Yvette, France

[#] ETH Zurich, Zurich, Switzerland

[«] Université de Lorraine, AgroParisTech, INRAE, Nancy, France

[»] Institute of Agricultural Sciences, ETH, Zurich, Switzerland

[»] Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, Brescia, Italy

[^] Technical University of Denmark, Lyngby, Denmark

[˘] University of Antwerpen, Antwerpen, Belgium

[‡] Wageningen University & Research, Wageningen, Netherlands

[?] Free University of Bozen-Bolzano, Bozen-Bolzano, Italy

[‡] Research Institute for Nature and Forest, INBO, Geraardsbergen, Belgium

[‡] Forest Research, Alice Holt, United Kingdom

[‡] Swiss Federal Research Institute WSL, Birmensdorf, Switzerland

Corresponding author: Rossella Guerrieri (rossellaguerrieri@gmail.com)

Received: 16 Feb 2025 | Published: 28 May 2025

Citation: Guerrieri R, Montedoro M, Rossi M, Mazzenga F, Aurela M, Berveille D, Buchmann N, Cuntz M, Delpierre N, Feigenwinter I, Gerosa G, Ibrom A, Lauriks F, Männikkö M, Marzuoli R, van der Molen M, Montagnani L, Neiryck J, Vanguelova E, Verstraeten A, Waldner P, Matteucci G (2025) Combining stable isotopes in tree rings and ecosystem fluxes to assess the effects of nitrogen deposition and climate extremes on European forests. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 8: e150416. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.8.e150416>

Abstract

Forest ecosystems are particularly threatened by global change components, i.e., more frequent extreme weather and climate events (particularly drought and heatwaves) and increasing (N) deposition, resulting in great uncertainties for the future of the essential ecological, economic and social benefits that humanity relies on from forests. Drought and heatwaves impair physiological mechanisms underpinning tree growth and forest productivity, and they may trigger tree mortality, thus constraining the forest carbon sink (Adams and i 2017; Gazol and Camarero 2022; Hartmann et al. 2022; Hubau 2020). On the one hand, N deposition stimulates tree growth in nitrogen-limited forests, under steady increase in atmospheric CO₂ (Etzold 2020; Fernández-Martínez 2017 ; Flechard 2020; Wang et al. 2017). On the other hand, increasing atmospheric N input above the empirical nitrogen critical load (above which harmful effects can occur in the ecosystem) (Braun et al. 2022)^(*) could reduce the positive effect on tree growth and could cause forest dieback, through soil acidification and nutrient imbalances, but also by making trees more vulnerable to climate extremes (Dalton et al. 2024; Etzold 2020; Ferretti et al. 2015; Flechard 2020; Gharun et al. 2021; Thomas et al. 2009). Many questions remain: How do these global change components interact and affect forest carbon, water and N cycling? Which tree ecophysiological mechanisms are involved? Are those mechanisms synchronized (in terms of magnitude and temporal trends) at tree and ecosystem scales? Does N deposition affect tree and forest responses to climate extremes?

The NEXTRES project aims at answering these questions by applying a multi-scale approach (from tree to ecosystem responses) to eleven forests along a climate and total N deposition gradient (from 3 to 42 kg ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹) across Europe, selected within established monitoring networks, namely ICOS and ICP Forests (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. [doi](#)

Location of the forest sites included in NEXTRES project.

We will present preliminary results combining existing ecosystem CO₂ and water vapor fluxes with dendroecological information on growth as well as stable carbon isotope ratios to explore multidecadal changes in water-use efficiency, and to elucidate underpinning tree physiological mechanisms. Moreover, we will target years characterized by climate extremes to follow the intra-annual carbon isotope fingerprint within individual in tree rings to evaluate possible divergences:

1. among tree species in their recovery strategies, and
2. between tree and ecosystem responses.

Finally, we will elucidate whether an excess of atmospheric N input can affect tree and forest responses to climate extremes.

Keywords

Dendroecology, Eddy covariance, carbon isotope composition, global change

Presenting author

Rossella Guerrieri

Presented at

ORAL

Funding program

NextGenerationEU under the National Recovery and Resilience Plan - Mission 4 Education and research - Component 2 From research to business - Investment 1.1 Notice Prin 2022 - DD N. 104 del 2/2/2022, proposal code 202299J927 - CUP J53D23002640006.

Grant title

Effects of nitrogen deposition and climate extremes on European forests: combining stable isotopes in tree rings and ecosystem fluxes (NEXTRES)

Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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